

A PROBABILISTIC FRAMEWORK FOR THE HOUGH TRANSFORM AND LEAST SQUARES POSE ESTIMATION

Jorge S. Marques

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
Instituto Superior Técnico
Av. Rovisco Pais, 1000 Lisboa, Portugal

ABSTRACT

The Hough transform and least squares pose estimation are usually considered as unrelated methods based on different assumptions. This paper presents a unified perspective of both approaches, in a probabilistic framework. It is shown that both methods compute maximum likelihood estimates of the object pose, based on different probability distributions. The main properties of the algorithms are discussed and their performance is characterized by Monte Carlo tests. This methodology can be extended to other shape representation algorithms.

1 INTRODUCTION

Shape alignment is a basic operation in many image analysis problems. The problem can be stated as follows: given a pair of curves, or surfaces, or images, we wish to estimate a geometric transformation which maps one of the shapes into the other. When this transformation is a rigid body motion (rotation+translation) it is denoted as a pose transformation since it defines a change of coordinates between two Cartesian frames.

Many algorithms were proposed to align shapes based on different types of features, different matching criteria and optimization methods, e.g., by using the interpretation tree[8], graph isomorphism, geometric hashing[12], pose clustering[15] or robust estimation methods such as Ransac[7] or LMeds[14].

The Hough transform (HT) and the least squares (LS) algorithm are two well known pose estimation methods. The HT detects an object and estimates the pose parameters by computing the largest subset of image features fitting a rigid template (shape model) modified by the pose transformation[3]. Its strong points are the ability to discard features belonging to other objects and the robustness against incomplete data. Its weakest point is, perhaps, the rigidity assumption which impairs the performance of the HT in the detection of deformed shapes. The LS method is based on the minimization of an objective function: the sum of squared distances between image features and the model. This requires the assignment of a model feature to each observed feature, known as matching. Since the pose is unknown, it is

not easy to define a reliable correspondence between the observed features and the model features and iterative estimation procedures are often used to overcome this difficulty[13, 4]. Furthermore, the LS method does not provide a natural mechanism to discard the influence of outliers (this difficulty can be alleviated by using robust LS techniques[9]). Despite these weaknesses, no rigidity assumption is required in the LS approach.

This paper presents a unified perspective of the Hough transform and least squares method, in a probabilistic framework. Assuming that the image features are realizations of random variables, it is shown that both methods compute maximum likelihood estimates of the object pose, based on different probability distributions. The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly reviews the HT and LS pose estimation. Section 3 formulates both methods in a maximum likelihood framework. Section 4 provides an experimental evaluation of both algorithms under controlled conditions and Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 PROBLEM FORMULATION

Let us consider two shapes, the reference shape and the observed shape, represented by two sets of points: $X, Y \subset R^n$, ($n=2$ or 3). It will be assumed that each point $y \in Y$ is the image of a point $x \in X$ corrupted by additive noise η , i.e.,

$$y = Tx + \eta \quad (1)$$

where T is a geometric transformation, parametrized by a vector of unknown parameters, and η is an error which accounts for shape deformation, measurement noise and finite sampling of the observed shape. Several transformations are used to align pairs of 2D or 3D shapes: e.g., affine transforms, projective transforms. In this paper, we shall adopt a rigid body transformation.

Two pose estimation methods are briefly reviewed in the sequel: the Hough transform and the least squares algorithm.

2.1 Hough transform

Let $f(y, \theta), f : R^n \times R^p \rightarrow R$, be an implicit model of the observed contour or surface where θ is a vector of

unknown pose and shape parameters. Let $g(y, \theta)$ be the shape characteristic function

$$g(y, \theta) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } f(y, \theta) = 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Let Y be a set of observations. The Hough transform is defined by[11]

$$H(\theta) = \sum_{y \in Y} g(y, \theta) \quad (3)$$

i.e., it counts the number of times equation $f(y, \theta) = 0$ is verified (the number of data points which belong to the curve or surface, for each value of θ). A single object is detected by computing the global maximum of $H(\theta)$. Therefore, the estimation of pose (and shape) is

$$\hat{\theta}_{HT} = \arg \max_{\theta} H(\theta) \quad (4)$$

Assuming that the shape model is a set of points X , f will be zero for a given choice of θ , if y is the image of one of the model points obtained with the pose transformation. In practice, we will assume that f is zero in the vicinity of the transformed point, i.e.,

$$g(y, \theta) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \min_{x \in X} \|y - (Rx + t)\| < D \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where R is a rotation matrix and t is a translation vector. It is implicitly assumed that $\|\eta\| < D$. If $n=2$, matrix R is defined by

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \alpha & -\sin \alpha \\ \sin \alpha & \cos \alpha \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where α is a rotation angle while in 3D space, a rotation depends on three independent variables (e.g., three Euler angles). Vector θ contains the rotation angles and the translation vector.

2.2 Least squares method

The least squares pose estimation requires a correspondence between the observed features and model features. This relationship is computed using a matching algorithm. Matching can either be obtained by optimal techniques (e.g., by using an interpretation tree[8]) or by sub-optimal and faster ways, using heuristic criteria, e.g., the closest point criterion[4].

Let $\{x_1, \dots, x_M\}$ be a subset of X and $\{y_1, \dots, y_M\}$ a subset of Y such that y_k is associated to x_k according to a given matching criterion and let $x_1(\theta), \dots, x_M(\theta)$ be the images of the model features after being modified by a pose transformation (rotation+translation) parametrized by θ .

The LS estimate of θ is obtained by the minimization of an objective function

$$E(\theta) = \sum_i \|y_i - x_i(\theta)\|^2 \quad (7)$$

Therefore,

$$\hat{\theta}_{LS} = \arg \min_{\theta} E(\theta) \quad (8)$$

The minimization of (7) can be performed by using the singular value decomposition of the cross covariance [2] or by using quaternions[10]. Robust least squares are also used to reduce the influence of outliers on pose estimates[9].

3 PROBABILISTIC INTERPRETATION

Let us formulate the HT and the LS algorithm as maximum likelihood (ML) estimation methods. Let $Y = (Y_1, \dots, Y_M)$ be a sequence of M independent random variables and let $p_k(y_k; \theta)$ be the probability density function of Y_k , denoted here as the observation model; $\theta \in R^p$ is a vector containing the unknown parameters of all distributions. The ML estimate of θ , given a realization $y = (y_1, \dots, y_M)$ of the random sequence Y is

$$\hat{\theta} = \arg \max_{\theta} l(\theta) \quad (9)$$

where

$$l(\theta) = \sum_i \log p_i(y_i; \theta) \quad (10)$$

is the log-likelihood function¹. The HT and the LS method are special cases of the ML approach. They correspond to specific choices of the observation model $p_k(y_k; \theta)$.

Let us first assume that p_k is a Gibbs distribution based on the shape characteristic function

$$p_k(y_k; \theta) = C(\theta) e^{g(y_k, \theta)} \quad (11)$$

where $C(\theta)$ is a normalization constant defined by²

$$C(\theta) = \frac{1}{\int e^{g(y, \theta)} dy} \quad (12)$$

Replacing (11) in (10), the log-likelihood function becomes

$$l(\theta) = \sum_i \log C(\theta) + g(y_i, \theta) \quad (13)$$

which can be rewritten as follows

$$l(\theta) = K(\theta) + H(\theta) \quad (14)$$

Assuming that K does not depend on θ (this is true in the case of pose transformations), the log-likelihood function is the Hough transform plus a constant. Thus, the ML algorithm is equivalent to the maximization of the Hough transform.

Now, let us assume that η is a random variable with normal distribution, $N(0, \sigma^2)$. If there is no information concerning the model feature which generated the observation y_k , then

$$p(y_k; \theta) = \sum_{x \in X} p(y_k, x; \theta) \quad (15)$$

¹it is assumed that $p_i(y_i; \theta) > 0, \forall y_i$

² y_k is restricted to an interval of R^n to keep the integral finite

Figure 1: a) reference shape and observation models of the b) HT and c) LS method

and therefore

$$p(y_k; \theta) = \sum_{x \in X} P(x) \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{n/2} \sigma^n} e^{-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \|y_k - x(\theta)\|^2} \quad (16)$$

This is a mixture of Gaussians. Each Gaussian is centered at a transformed model point $x(\theta)$ and its weight $P(x)$ is the probability of the model feature x .

Matching attempts to associate pairs of model/ observed features. Matching could be conceived in a probabilistic framework by assigning a probability to all possible pairs of features. In practice, matching algorithms produce hard deIn this case, the observation model (16) becomes a Gaussian density

$$p(y_k; \theta) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{n/2} \sigma^n} e^{-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \|y_k - x_k(\theta)\|^2} \quad (17)$$

centered at the transformed point $x_k(\theta)$ and the log-likelihood function (10) is

$$l(\theta) = K - \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} E(\theta) \quad (18)$$

where $E(\theta)$ is the objective function minimized by the LS algorithm. Therefore, LS is a special case of the ML technique, when the observation model is a multivariate normal distribution centered at one of the points of the transformed shape model. It should be noted that (17) is strongly dependent on the matching output.

Fig. 1 shows the observation models associated with the Hough transform and with the least squares algorithm. Fig. 1a shows the reference shape after the pose transformation. Fig. 1b,c display the observation models, $p(y_k; \theta)$, associated with the HT and with the LS algorithm (assuming that the observation was produced by the 10th model feature). There are two main differences between these distributions: i) in LS, the density function is high only in the vicinity of the transformed model feature associated with y_k while the density of the HT is high in the vicinity of all model features; ii) in LS, the observation model is Gaussian and tends to

Figure 2: a-c) shape model and deformed shapes obtained with $\sigma = .03, .05, .07$; aligned shapes using the d-f) HT and g-i) LS method

zero when the observation moves away from the transformed shape; the observation model of the HT does not.

4 RESULTS

Experimental tests were performed to evaluate both algorithms in the presence of shape deformation and outliers. The model adopted in these tests is a sequence of 20 2D points, which was manually defined and normalized using the l^2 norm. The synthetic data was generated by transforming the model features according to (1), using random pose parameters (α, t are r.v. with uniform distribution in $[0, 2\pi[$, $[-X, X]^2$, respectively) and observation noise with normal distribution $N(0, \sigma^2 I)$. Matching was assumed to be known in LS experiments.

Figs 2a-c show the reference shape and distorted shapes generated with $\sigma = .03, .05, .07$. Figs. 2d-i show the shape alignment performed by the HT and LS algorithm. LS performs better in these examples. It has a remarkable capacity to correctly estimate the pose parameters even when the observed shape is strongly deformed. These conclusions were verified by Monte Carlo tests performed with $\sigma = 0.01, 0.02, \dots, 0.10$ (see Fig. 4a). In each case, 200 shapes were randomly generated and aligned by both algorithms. The results were evaluated by the average value of the l^2 norm D ($D = \sqrt{E}$). The LS method performs always better in this example and it is clearly superior when $\sigma > .05$.

Fig. 3 shows the results obtained with outliers: we have replaced some of the observations by random features generated with uniform distribution in the interval $[-1, 1]^2$. The modified observations were randomly selected as well as their value. Fig. 3 shows the alignment results obtained with 10%, 20% and 30% of outliers. The performance of the HT is clearly superior as expected since it retrieves the correct pose in all the examples. This superiority is also observed in the Monte Carlo results displayed in Fig. 4b. The matching crite-

Figure 3: a-c) shape model and observed shapes with 10%, 20% and 30% of outliers; aligned shapes using the d-f) HT and g-i) LS method

tion D was computed using valid data points only (the terms corresponding to the outliers were removed and E was normalized by the number of valid terms). The performance of the LS method is severely affected by the presence of outliers while the HT shows a remarkable robustness in the presence of outliers provided that the number of outliers is smaller than 60%.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper formulates the HT and the LS method as maximum likelihood estimators of the shape pose. The data density adopted by the HT has two levels: a higher level in the vicinity of the (transformed) model features and a lower (non-zero) level outside this region. All the observations which lie near the reference shape, after being transformed according to the pose estimates, receive a high score. The other observations (e.g., outliers) receive a lower score, independent of the feature location. The LS method is different. The observation model used in LS depends on a prior matching of the data with the model features. If there is a matching error, the observation is severely penalized even if it is in the vicinity of the other model features. The score tends to minus infinity when the error increases. The outliers dominate the log likelihood function and the pose estimates become meaningless. These conclusions are supported by the results of Monte Carlo tests performed under controlled conditions.

The methodology adopted in this paper can be extended to other pose estimation methods and provides a link to the work developed in the context of deformable models (e.g., see[5, 6, 1]).

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Figure 4: Monte Carlo results with a) deformed shapes and b) outliers

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